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Research Article

**CONSEQUENCE OF LESION SIZE ON THE FREQUENCY OF
PNEUMOTHORAX AFTER CT GUIDED TRANSTHORACIC
NEEDLE ASPIRATION BIOPSY OF LUNG MASSES**¹Dr Fatima Tariq, ²Dr Farwa Sarwar, ³Dr Muhammad Rizwan¹Sheikh Zaid Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan²Multan Medical & Dental College, Multan³Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim of the study: To analyze the incidence of pneumothorax after TNAB in CT-controlled lung tumors and to correlate it with the size of the lesion.

Patients and Methods: This study was held in the Radiology department of Sheikh Zaid Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan for one-year duration from August 2019 to August 2020. Seventy patients underwent CT guided FNA of the chest masses.

Results: Out of seventy 18 patients, ie; 26% developed pneumothorax. Lesion less than 1 cm, out of 6 patients 3 developed pneumothorax (50 %), lesions 1-2 cm 5 out of 11 developed pneumothorax (45%), lesions with size of 2-3 cm 5 out of 14 patients developed pneumothorax (35%), lesions between 3-4cm 2 out of 8 developed pneumothorax (25%), lesion sized 4-5 cm 1 out of 15 developed pneumothorax (6%), and lesion with more than 5 cm size 1 out of 16 developed pneumothorax (6%)

Conclusion: The study shows that the incidence of pneumothorax after CT guided TNAB of Lung Masses increases with the decrease in lesion size.

Key words: pneumothorax, CT-guided TNAB, lesion size.

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INTRODUCTION:

Percutaneous transthoracic biopsy of lung tumors is a long-known and proven invasive method. Clinicians rely heavily on radiological and pathological findings to make a diagnosis. In the previous days, open lung biopsy was performed to establish diagnosis, but as the drug developed, newer methods of body imaging and guiding an invasive radiologist appeared, open lung biopsy has now become almost obsolete. Computed tomography (CT)-assisted fine needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) of lung masses is currently used very often in cases where the diagnosis depends on histopathology. The CT images direct the radiologist towards the area of interest and the procedure is then complete. Percutaneous transthoracic lung aspiration biopsy (TNAB) is a well-established method of obtaining pulmonary tissue for pathological examination. The accuracy in recognizing benign and malignant diseases is over 80% and 90%, respectively. Fatal complications of systemic air embolism, hemorrhage, or pericardial tamponade have been reported, but these complications are rare. Other serious complications, such as seeding of malignant cells in the needle pathway, lung torsion, and empyema, are also rare and should not alter the indication for TNAB. Pneumothorax is by far the most common complication of surgery: Reported rates range from 5% to 61%. Most of these data relate to TNAB under fluoroscopic guidance. In general, TNABs performed under computed tomography (CT) guidance may be associated with a higher incidence of pneumothorax than fluoroscopic TNABs, possibly because CT takes longer and the average lesion size is smaller. The reported rate of pneumothorax with a CT biopsy may also be slightly higher as CT is more sensitive to detecting pneumothorax. Several studies have reported a 22–45% risk of pneumothorax with CT-guided TNAB. There are many factors or variables that influence the incidence of pneumothorax in FNAB CT-guided chest masses. The size of the needle, the size of the lesion, the depth of the lesion from the pleural surface, and the number of punctures made through the pleura are perhaps some of the important ones that have been studied in detail. Also, the residence time of the needle in the thoracic cavity, the residence time and the puncture angle of the pleura have been described as factors that have some influence on the development of pneumothorax following FNAB of the chest masses under the control of CT.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

Study design. It was a descriptive study held in the Radiology department of Sheikh Zaid Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan for one-year duration from August 2019 to August 2020. Seventy patients underwent CT guided FNA of the chest masses. Patients with a chest masses who required a biopsy to establish a definitive diagnosis. These patients were referred from thoracic medicine, thoracic surgery and medical departments. Convenient sampling was done.

Inclusion criterion

- 1 Patients between 15- 75 years age group.
2. The patients had a control X ray Chest and CT chest with them before the FNA.
3. All patients had PT/ APTT done for bleeding and clotting control

Exclusion Criterion

1. Due to complications that may result from the procedure, only patients in closed rooms were included in the study.
2. Already diagnosed cases were not taken into account.
3. Patients who did not receive an appropriate advice form from the appropriate consultant were also not considered.

METHODOLOGY:

Fine needle aspiration (FNA) was performed under the control of a Toshiba Spiral CT Xvision / Ex computer tomograph. The FNA was carried out by 18G, 20G or 22G. The size of the lesion, the distance of the lesion from the pleura and the number of pleural punctures recorded and documented in the appropriate proforma. Immediately after surgery, a chest CT scan and a 6-hour delayed chest X-ray were collected for pneumothorax analysis.

Data analysis.

In this descriptive study, the data, i.e., the effect of needle size, lesion size, lesion distance from pleura and number of pleural punctures on the incidence of pneumothorax following FNA of CT-guided chest masses was assessed using Proportions, Frequencies (%).

RESULTS:

The total number of patients enrolled in the study was 70. Eighteen of these 70 patients developed pneumothorax after surgery. Lesion less than 1cm, out of 6 patients 3 developed pneumothorax (50%), lesions 1-2cm 5 out of 11 developed pneumothorax (45%), lesions with size of 2-3cm 5 out of 14 patients developed pneumothorax (35%), lesions between 3-4cm 2 out of 8 developed pneumothorax (25%), lesion sized 4-5cm 1 out of 15 developed

pneumothorax (6%), and lesion with more than 5cm

size 1 out of 16 developed pneumothorax (6%).

Size of Lesion	=n	Pneumothorax	Frequency
<1cm	6	3	50%
1-2cm	11	5	45.4%
2-3cm	14	5	35%
3-4cm	8	2	25%
4-5cm	15	1	6%
>5cm	16	1	6%
	70	18	

Fig 1. Marking of the lesion and localization before biopsy

Fig 2. Needle insertion into the lesion close to hilum, no pneumothorax

Fig. 3. Pneumothorax during the procedure of TNAB

DISCUSSION:

The incidence of pneumothorax has been studied very extensively using many variables, with the lesion size being one. The size of the needle, the depth of the lesion, the number of punctures needed to obtain the appropriate samples, the residence time and the angle of the needle relative to the pleura were also examined. The strong correlation between the

incidence of pneumothorax and the size of the lesion is difficult to explain, although this correlation has been previously described. It can be argued that larger lesions will more often come into contact with the pleural surface and therefore do not require the needle to pass through the aerated lung. However, the correlation between the increase in the incidence of pneumothorax and the decreasing lesion size persists,

even if the lesions with pleural contact are not taken into account. Another possible explanation for this finding is that an up and down movement of the needle tip during an aspiration biopsy causes the adjacent parenchyma to tear more when the lesion is relatively small. All the cases we did were not attached to the pleura and the lesions were on the lungs, so the pleura had to be punctured.

CONCLUSIONS:

The study shows that the incidence of pneumothorax after TNAB of CT-guided lung tumors increases with the decrease in lesion size.

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